

Mafb nuclear factor expression in TE commitment in utero.

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We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of MafB as a lineage commitment factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

Citations

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